

Modeling and Prediction of Zinc Extraction Efficiency from Concentrate by Operating Condition and Using Artificial Neural Networks

Authors : S. Mousavian, D. Ashouri, F. Mousavian, V. Nikkhah Rashidabad, N. Ghazinia

Abstract : PH, temperature, and time of extraction of each stage, agitation speed, and delay time between stages effect on efficiency of zinc extraction from concentrate. In this research, efficiency of zinc extraction was predicted as a function of mentioned variable by artificial neural networks (ANN). ANN with different layer was employed and the result show that the networks with 8 neurons in hidden layer has good agreement with experimental data.

Keywords : zinc extraction, efficiency, neural networks, operating condition

Conference Title : ICCCMS 2014 : International Conference on Computer, Computational and Mathematical Sciences

Conference Location : Zurich, Switzerland

Conference Dates : January 14-15, 2014